

The Unjournal

Evaluation 1 of "Replicability & Generalisability: A Guide to CEA discounts"

Evaluator 1 (anonymous) for The Unjournal

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Pro:

- Raises important points and brings them to wider attention in simple language
- Good at thinking about individual RCTs [DR: Maybe you meant "Useful for considering *individual* RCTs"?]

Con:

- Not clear enough about intended use cases and framing. Writing should be clearer, shorter, more purposeful.
- Guidelines need more clarity and precision before they can be genuinely used. I think best to reframe this as a research note, rather than a ready-to-use 'guideline'..
- Unclear whether this is applicable to considering multiple studies and doing meta-analysis..